

**INNOVATION METHOD OF TEACHING VOCABULARY IN THE
SECOND LANGUAGE CLASSROOM**

Berdiqulov Shohmurod Elmurod o'g'li

Samarqand Davlat Chet tillari Instituti magistrant.

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Abstract: It is critical to assert that, because English has emerge as a standard and dominant supply to speak withinside the world, the hobby of getting to know this language is growing dramatically. But humans can't use any languages with out vocabulary and this paper analyses the vocabulary of a language and vocabulary coaching techniques and strategies and research a few techniques.

Keywords: Classroom, Method and approach, skill, vocabulary, phrases.

From the historic instances till present. Humanity is alive with their communique capabilities and phrases they use. Vocabulary of a language is similar to bricks of a excessive building. Rudyard Kipling says that phrases are the maximum effective drug used with the aid of using mankind. Additionally it's miles important that ,vocabulary is inextracably related with grammar, the receptive (listening and reading) and the productive (speakme and writing) abilities. Wilkins rightly says, "Without grammar little or no may be conveyed....however with out vocabulary not anything may be conveyed".Therefore the take a look at of vocabulary is on the middle whilst mastering a brand new language. No depend English being a second language or overseas language, one wishes to study vocabulary withinside the systematic way. If we cause to make use of language efficiently and clearly, we should have good inventory of vocabulary. Especially the English language is the richest to phrases. Thornbury opines: "If you spend maximum of some time analyzing grammar, your English will now no longer enhance very much. You will see maximum improvement, in case you research extra phrases and expressions. You can say little or no with grammar, however you may say almost whatever with phrases." In accordance together along with his factor of view , these days contemporary-day pedagogy face a few demanding situations the way to broaden coaching abilities, techniques and revolutionary strategies of vocabulary in addition to the use of phrases in actual life. Because of contemporary-day researches ,observations and stories freshmen may be knowledgeable through instructors higher through instructors and withinside the following a few beneficial sorts of strategies will be brought with the intention to gain greater exciting and qualitative lessons.

1. Actual items and displaying fashions. This method brings numerous income to

train vocabulary to the beginners. The names of many stuff may be taught through displaying real items. It offers actual enjoy and experience to the freshmen. For example, pen, chalk, table, chair, book, football, flowers, tomato etc. which might be each student have of their luggage or home, can be trained withinside the classroom. Real gadgets or fashions of actual items are very effective and significant in displaying meanings. through this approach students can memorize new phrases without problems because of their actuality.

2. Synonyms :Using synonyms are simply appropriate manner to enhance vocabulary of young learners. A synonym can be used to assist the scholar to parent out the exceptional sun sunglasses of meaning, if the synonym is higher recognized than the phrase being taught. Synonyms help to enhance a pupil's vocabulary financial institution and offer opportunity phrases instantly. These may be powerful considering the fact that they construct on phrases and terms that college students already recognize. Also, synonyms serve now no longer most effective to create very appealing and ordinary communication however additionally each person can take into account each phrase quicker and strive to use and seek your self extra instructional and significant equal of a phrase. This fashion is likewise endorsed even for destiny IELTS (International English Language Testing System) applicants to boom their vocabulary. Because in step with the requirements of all components of the IELTS exam, each candidate need to display his or her capacity to apply unique phrases of their vocabulary financial institution with a purpose to higer mark.. Besides that, as a supportive supply of this approach innovative educators should make crosswords, phrase snakes or different puzzles for college kids with the usage of those synonyms.

3. Homonyms: Homophones are phrases of the identical language which can be said alike even if they distinguish in spelling, meaning, or origin, such as "pair" and "pear". Homophones will also be spelled alike, as in "bear" (the animal) and "bear" (to carry). But this listing is composed simplest of homophones that aren't spelled alike. This method is without a doubt crucial to decorate vocabulary financial institution of college students in addition to their pronunciation. In the desk there are a few examples of homonyms: ant/aunt, ate/eight, bear/bare, son/sun, steal/steel, throne/thrown, blew/blue, beach/beechn, cent/scent/sent, cell/sel, census/senses die/dye...etc. This technique is in actually educational and thrilling to apply in the classroom, due to the fact at one look students will hurry to learn how to pronounce and even translate their meaning.

3. Role play: Role-play is to create the presence of a actual lifestyles state of affairs withinside the school room. It is extraordinarily vital withinside the lecture room conversation as it offers college students an possibility to exercise communicatively in distinct social contexts and in exclusive a social roles. The language carried out on this interest is various in line with the scholar's status, attitudes, mood, and exceptional situations. Furthermore , position – play assist to domesticate the feel of hobby to art , culture ,traditions which can be influncial to their conduct in addition to pupil can discover ways to use new phrases in actual lifestyles .Because , little portions of dramas or performs are verified as a actual and live . In 2006 , linguist Blachowicz said that, “Teachers can introduce a number of the phrases which provide each definitional and contextual records approximately the phrases to be discovered through making up a communicate for college kids so that scholars can recognize a in addition which means and utilization of the phrases.”

4. Video to provide of goal vocabulary: To make use of this technique educators are required to choose a video section that includes a chain of movements or visible element in line with their age, degree of knowledge, hobby, gender, outlook and religion. Richards said “When vocabulary phrases are being taught to scholars, instructors want to don't forget the way to educate those phrases to students primarily based totally at the ranges of ages, academic history and area of hobby. Next step is offering the novices with a listing of goal vocabulary phrases and ask them to assemble a paragraph that contains as a few of the phrases as possible. This hobby is satisfactory achieved after the freshmen have visible the video. As they discover ways to use extra vocabulary properly, instructor will see an development of their writing and speaking. As a function of “Resource” instructor also can display a quick movie with out sound and asking students to talk about what communicate they might count on to hear. Showing a scene from a movie with out sound and asking students to apply the facial features to decide emotion. Videos can be special including components of films, information comics or even brief cartoons that may introduce new phrases .Moreover, in line with facts the quantity of vocabulary that kids want to collect every 12 months is awesome in scope, expected to be approximately 3,000 phrases a text. Therefore, a complete technique have been brought to pedagogy which consists of the subsequent additives wishes to be in place.

- Use “instructional” examine-aloud events. The advice that mother and father and instructors study aloud to kids is most of the maximum famous tips withinside the discipline of reading.

• Systematically train college students the which means of prefixes, suffixes, and root phrases. The majority of English phrases had been created via the mixture of morphemic elements, that is, prefixes and suffixes with base phrases and phrase roots. Anderson and Freebody claimed that “If beginners recognize how this combinatorial manner works, they own one of the maximum effective understandings important for vocabulary growth.”By this concept it's far clarified that the use of prefixes, suffixes, and root phrases to broaden goal vocabulary can boost up studying process of latest phrases. By the manner of conclusion, it must be stated that , There isn't anyt any positive fire treatment or technique to beautify vocabulary in an afternoon or two. A student's vocabulary financial institution may be enriched on a sluggish foundation and one ought to usually display eager interest and exuberance in finding, mastering and expertise new phrases. Teaching vocabulary via incidental, intentional, and unbiased tactics requires instructors to devise a huge kind of sports and exercises.

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